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Effect of African Mistletoe (*Tapinanthus globiferus*) (A. Rich) Tiegh) on Vegetative Growth of Host Tree Species in Wamakko, Sokoto, Sudan Savanna Ecological Zone, Nigeria

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This research was carried out to investigate the effect African Mistletoes (*Tapinanthus globiferus*) on the vegetative growth of host tree species. It involved seven sampling locations within Wamakko LGA that were earmarked for the study. Measurements of stem DBH, plant height and canopy spread were conducted. The research work identified 569 host trees in the sample sites representing 12 species, belonging to eight families' and 11 genera. *A. indica* had a DBH of 0.72m, which was significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) than of *G. aborea* and *A. lebbeck* (0.73 each). Similarly, *G. aborea* and *A. lebbeck* had a plant height of 9.67m each which differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) from 9.10m of *A. indica*. However, *A. lebbeck* had significantly higher ($P > 0.05$) canopy spread (44.60m) than *G. aborea* (23.90m) and *A. indica* (11.54m). The DBH of both host species, *G. aborea* (10.59m), *A. nilotica* (0.54m), *A. indica* (0.49m) and *E. camaldulensis* (0.25m) indicated significant differences ($P < 0.05$) from each other. . So also plant height of *E. camaldulensis* (9.36m), *A. indica* (9.38m), *A. nilotica* (9.27m) and *G. aborea* (9.20m). There was no significant difference ($P > 0.05$) in canopy spread between *G. aborea* (19.72m), *A. nilotica* (12.63m), *A. indica* (9.26m) and *E. camaldulensis* (7.91m). UDUTH host trees had highest DBH range (72m-73m) and UAS Polytechnic had the least (11m-12m). *Azadirachta indica* at CCNN Sokoto was the tallest (17.73m), *E. camaldulensis* at SSCOE was the shortest (3.02m). *Albizia lebbeck* at UDUTH had the widest canopy (44.60m). *Mangifera indica* at CCNN, Sokoto had the least canopy spread (2.95m). This indicated that infestations by *T. globiferus* was found on growth parameters of host trees in the areas. Hence, the need to reduce its growth through historical slashing and pruning.

Key words: *Tapinanthus globiferus*; Sudan Savanna; Wamakko; Vegetative Growth; Tree Species

INTRODUCTION

Mistletoe belongs to the kingdom Plantae, subkingdom Tracheobionta, division Magnoliophyta, subdivision Spermatophyta, class Magnoliopsida, subclass Rosidae, Family Loranthaceae, order Santales, genus *Tapinanthus*, Species *globiferus*. Recent phylogenetic studies confirm that mistletoes belong to five distinct

Families Misodendronaceae, Eremolepidaceae, Santalaceae, Viscaceae, Loranthaceae. (Der and Nickrent, 2008; Vidal Russell and Nickrent, 2008). Loranthaceae which is the largest family having about 75 genera according to Judd *et al.* (2002) among them the major genera found in Nigeria are six, namely: *Tapinanthus*, *Agelanthus*, *Loranthus*, *Globimetula*, *Phragmanthera* and *Englerina*. Mistletoes consists of about 1400 species around the world (Judd *et al.*, 2002) *Tapinanthus* is far widely spread in the Nigerian savanna

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(Dlama *et al.*, 2016).

Mistletoes is locally called “Kauci” in Hausa language, ‘Afomo’ in Yoruba and ‘Apari’ in Igbo language. It is called Children’s matches in eastern Cameroon, presumably due to the matches like shape of the flower (Oluwole *et al.*, 2013). It is also known by the common names of Bird lime and All heal. All mistletoes are hemiparasites, bearing evergreen leaves that photosynthesize, but depend on their host mainly for water and mineral nutrient (Mulus. 2000). These mistletoes grow on wide range of host trees and may reduce the growth, productivity and may eventually kill the host trees with heavy infestation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted at Wamakko, Sokoto State Sudan Savanna Ecological zone Nigeria with Longitude ranges from $11^{\circ} 3'$ to $13^{\circ} 50' E$ and Latitude ranges 4° to

$6^{\circ} 40' N$. As for topography, the state is characterized by gentle undulating plains that rise from an elevation of about 300m above the sea level in the Northwest to an average of 460m above the sea level. (Adegboyega *et al.*, 2015). The vegetation zone of Sokoto is Sudan Savanna with sparse trees, shrubs and dominant grasses. The state has the climatic condition of semi-arid with two distinct seasons, the wet season which lasts from June to September; with an annual rainfall ranges between 300mm and 800 mm at the Peak of rainfall is reached in August while mean annual temperature is $34.5^{\circ}C$ with dry seasons with temperature often exceeding $40^{\circ}C$. Generally climate change and global warming has significant impact on society and environment (IPCC, 2007).

The research covered seven selected sites in Wammako Local Government Area (LGA) Sokoto State, namely, Usmanu Danfodiyo University Teaching Hospital (UDUTH), Government Day Secondary School (GDSS) Arkilla, Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto (UDUS),

Figure 1: Map of the study Area showing the study sites in Wamakko LGA, Sokoto State.
Source: G I S Unit, Department of Geography Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto (2019)

Table 1: Effects of African Mistletoe (*Tapinanthus globiferus*) on Vegetative Growth Parameters of Host Tree Species at Usmanu Danfodiyo University Teaching Hospital, Sokoto (Site One)

Host Species	Number of Host Trees	DBH (m)	Plant Height (m) Canopy Spread (m)	Canopy Spread (m)
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	59	0.72 ^b	9.10 ^b 11.54 ^b	11.54 ^b
<i>Gmelina aborea</i>	27	0.73 ^a	9.67 ^a 23.90 ^b	23.90 ^b
<i>Albizia lebbbeck</i>	3	0.73 ^a	9.67 ^a 44.60 ^a	44.60 ^a
Total	89			
SE±		0.005	0.329 16.704	16.704
Significant		*	* *	*

Means in a column followed by same letter (s) are not significantly different ($P < 0.05$) at 5% level using LSD. Significant.

Table 2: Effects of African Mistletoe (*Tapinanthus globiferus*) on Vegetative Growth Parameters of Host Tree Species at Government Day Secondary School Arkilla (Site Two).

Host Species	Number of Host Trees	DBH (m)	Plant Height (m) Canopy Spread (m)	Canopy Spread (m)
<i>Eucalyptus camaldulensis</i>				
	11	0.25 ^d	9.36 ^b	7.91 ^a
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	21	0.49 ^c	9.38 ^b	9.26 ^a
<i>Acacia nilotica</i>	11	0.54 ^b	9.27 ^c	12.63 ^a
<i>Gmelina aborea</i>	5	0.59 ^a	9.20 ^d	19.72 ^a
Total	48			
SE±		0.151	0.083	5.281
Significant		*	*	*

Means in a column followed by same letter (s) are not significantly different ($P < 0.05$) at 5% level using LSD. *= Significant.

Table 3: Effects of African Mistletoe (*Tapinanthus globiferus*) on Vegetative Growth Parameters of Host Tree Species at Usmanu Danfodiyo University main campus, Sokoto (Site Three)

Host Species	Number of Host Trees	DBH (m)	Plant Height (m) Canopy Spread (m)	Canopy Spread (m)
<i>Acacia nilotica</i>	22	0.32 ^b	9.60 ^b	7.76 ^a
<i>Balanites aegyptiaca</i>	7	0.32 ^b	12.09 ^a	7.80 ^a
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	33	0.40 ^a	10.28 ^a	7.22 ^a
<i>Ficus polita</i>	4	0.28 ^c	9.20 ^b	5.84 ^b
<i>Terminalia mantali</i>	11	0.26 ^d	13.21 ^a	7.48 ^a
Total	77			
SE±		0.054	1.711	0.806
Significant		*	*	*

Means in a column followed by same letter (s) are not significantly different ($P < 0.05$) at 5% level using LSD. *= Significant.

Cement Company of Northern Nigeria (CCNN), Shehu Shagari College of Education (SSCOE), RIMA television and Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic Sokoto (UASP) (see figure 1). Purposive sampling was used to collect *Tapinanthus globiferus* on host trees species (Gilbertson and Pyatt, 1990; Patton, 2002; Suri, 2011). Field investigation was focused on the level of occurrence,

species composition status, level of distribution, abundance and effect on host trees species.

A total of seven sites were purposively selected for the study in replicates. A 100m long measuring tape was used to measure the selected area and ranging poles to demarcate them. One hundred square metres (100m²) area was demarcated in two replicates. (Patton, 2002;

Table 4: Effects of African Mistletoe (*Tapinanthus globiferus*) on Vegetative Growth Parameters of Host Tree Species At Cement Company of Northern Nigeria, Sokoto. (Site Four).

Host Species	Number of Host Trees	DBH (m)	Plant Height (m) Canopy Spread (m)	Canopy Spread (m)
<i>Terminalia catappa</i>	30	0.47 ^a	11.62 ^b 7.09 ^b	7.09 ^b
<i>Albizia lebbbeck</i>	2	0.34 ^f	11.20 ^b 9.21 ^a	9.21 ^a
<i>Delonix regia</i>	3	0.38 ^b	12.83 ^b 10.61 ^a	10.61 ^a
<i>Mangifera indica</i>	4	0.36 ^e	12.50 ^b 2.95 ^c	2.95 ^c
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	26	0.38 ^b	17.73 ^a 6.03 ^d	6.03 ^d
Total	65			
SE±		0.049	2.629 2.963	2.963
Significant		*	* *	*

Means in a column followed by same letter (s) are not significantly different (P<0.05) at 5% level using LSD. *= Significant.

Table 5: Effects of African Mistletoe (*Tapinanthus globiferus*) on Vegetative Growth Parameters of Host Tree Species at Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto (Site Five).

Host Species	Number of Host Trees	DBH (m)	Plant Height (m) Canopy Spread(m)	Canopy Spread (m)
<i>Eucalyptus camaldulensis</i>	19	0.38 ^e	3.02 ^b 7.39 ^b	7.39 ^b
<i>Balanite aegyptiaca</i>	1	0.39 ^b	6.80 ^c 8.90 ^c	8.90 ^c
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	73	0.36 ^d	9.0 ^c 11.11 ^a	11.11 ^a
<i>Albizia lebbbeck</i>	4	0.48 ^a	11.65 ^c 7.47	7.47
Total	97			
SE±		0.053	3.651 1.739	1.739
Significant		*	* *	*

Means in a column followed by same letter (s) are not significantly different (P<0.05) at 5% level using LSD. *= Significant.

Suri, 2011). At each of the study area, infested host tree species were harvested by using "Go- to- hell" instrument to pluck the mistletoes and by hand picking on shorter trees BCMF (1996) and Blanco *et al.* (2006). The samples collected were taken to the Herbarium of the Department of Biological Sciences Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto for identification and certification. The measurements of the trunk DBH (diameter breath and height) of various ranges were and height of the trees was measured using Haga Altimeter. Data generated from the study were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using SPSS. Differences between sample means were separated using Duncan's new multiple range Test(DNMRT).Significant differences among the variables were determined at 5% level of significance ((P>0.05) (Shaffer and Juliet, 1999).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results in table 1 (Site one) showed the mean DBH, plant height and canopy spread (m) of the infested host tree species across seven study sites of the study area. At site one, *A. indica* had a DBH of 0.72m, which was significantly higher (P<0.05) than *G. aborea* and *A. lebbbeck* (0.73 each). Similarly, *G. aborea* and *A. lebbbeck* had a plant height of 9.67m each which differed significantly (P<0.05) from 9.10m of *A. indica*. However, canopy spread of *A. lebbbeck* reached 44.60m which was significantly higher (P> 0.05) than *G. aborea* (23.90m) and *A. indica* (11.54m). At site two (Table 2), the DBH of both host species, *G. aborea* (.59m), *A. nilotica* (0.54m), *A. indica* (0.49m) and *E. camaldulensis* (0.25m) indicated significant differences (P<0.05) from each other.

Table 6: Effects of African Mistletoe (*Tapinanthus globiferus*) on Vegetative Growth Parameters of Host Tree Species at Rima Television Sokoto (Site Six).

Host Species	Number of Host Trees	DBH (m)	Plant Height (m) Canopy Spread(m)	Canopy Spread (m)
<i>Albizia lebbbeck</i>	1	0.18 ^a	9.57 ^c 6.60 ^c	6.60 ^c
<i>Anacadium occidentale</i>	17	0.12 ^c	11.99 ^b 12.73 ^a	12.73 ^a
<i>Eucalyptus camaldulensis</i>	3	0.13 ^b	9.57 ^c 5.63 ^b	5.63 ^b
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	66	0.13 ^b	14.43 ^a 9.13 ^b	9.13 ^b
<i>Terminalia mantali</i>	12	0.13 ^b	12.54 ^b 7.56 ^{bc}	7.56 ^{bc}
Total SE±	99	0.024	2.079 2.778	2.778
Significance	*	*	*	*

Means in a column followed by same letter (s) are not significantly different ($P < 0.05$) at 5% level using LSD. * = Significant.

Table 7: Effects of African Mistletoe (*Tapinanthus globiferus*) on Vegetative Growth Parameters of Host Tree Species at Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic (Site Seven).

Host Species	Number of Host Trees	DBH (m)	Plant Height (m) Canopy Spread	Canopy Spread (m)
<i>Balanite aegyptiaca</i>	18	0.22 ^a	13.03 ^a	6.67 ^b
<i>Acacia nilotica</i>	27	0.12 ^b	10.14 ^b	7.88 ^a
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	49	0.11 ^c	13.63 ^a	7.39 ^a
Total SE	94	0.061	1,866	0.609
Significant		*	*	*

Means in a column followed by same letter (s) are not significantly different ($P < 0.05$) at 5% level using LSD. * = Significant.

Similarly, the height of *E. camaldulensis* (9.36m), *A. indica* (9.38m), *A. nilotica* (9.27m) and *G. aborea* (9.20m). There was no significant difference ($P > 0.05$) in canopy spread between *G. aborea* (19.72m), *A. nilotica* (12.63m), *A. indica* (9.26m) and *E. camaldulensis* (7.91m).

The results in table 3 (site three) showed the DBH of *A. nilotica* and *B. aegyptiaca* (0.32m each) differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) from *A. indica* (0.40m), *F. polita* (0.28m) and *T. mantali* (0.26m). Likewise, plant height of *B. aegyptiaca* (12.09m), *A. indica* (10.28m) and *T. mantali* (13.21m) were significantly higher than ($P < 0.05$) from those of *A. nilotica* (9.60m) and *F. polita* (9.20m). The lower canopy spread of *F. polita* (5.84m) differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) from those of *B. aegyptiaca* (7.80m), *A. nilotica* (7.76m), *T. mantali* (7.48m) and *A. indica* (7.22m). The results in table 4 (site four) showed that significant differences ($P < 0.05$) occurred between DBH of *T. catapa* (0.47m), *A. lebbbeck* (0.34m), *M. indica* (0.36m) and that of *D. regia* and *A. indica* (0.38m). Similarly, canopy spread of *T. catapa* (7.09m) and *M. indica* (2.95m) both differ significantly ($P < 0.05$) from those of *D. regia* (10.61) and *A. lebbbeck* (9.21m). There is no significant difference ($P > 0.05$) in plant height

between *T. catapa* (11.62m), *A. lebbbeck* (11.20m) *D. regia* (12.83m) and *M. indica* (12.50m). But both of them differ significantly ($P < 0.05$) in height from *A. indica* (17.73m).

The results in table 5 (Site five) showed significant differences ($P < 0.05$) in both three parameters between the host species. The DBH of *E. camaldulensis* (0.38m) *B. aegyptiaca* (0.39m), *A. indica* (0.36m) and *A. lebbbeck* (0.48m) all differ significantly ($P < 0.05$) from each other. The canopy spread of *E. camaldulensis* (7.39m), *B. aegyptiaca* (8.90m), *A. indica* (11.11m) and *A. lebbbeck* (7.47m) both differ significantly ($P < 0.05$). Plant height of *B. aegyptiaca* (6.80m), *A. indica* (9.0m) and *A. lebbbeck* (11.65m) do not differ significantly ($P > 0.05$) with exception of *E. camadulensis* (3.02m).

Host parameters contained in table 6 (site six) showed that *A. lebbbeck* had DBH of 0.18m and *A. occidentale* (0.12) differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) from each other and form that of the other three species at the site. They were *E. camaldulensis*, *A. indica* and *T. mantali* with DBH of 0.13meaach. The height of *T. Mantali* (12.54m) and *A. occidentale* (11.99m) did not differ significantly ($P > 0.05$), so also those of *A. lebbbeck* and *E. camaldulensis* (9.57m) each. However, the two species differed significantly

($P < 0.05$) form that of *A. indica* (14.43m). The canopy spread of *T. mantali* (7.56m), *A. lebbeck* (6.60m) and *E. camaldulensis* in the location did not differ significantly ($P > 0.05$). But those of *A. occidentalis* (12.73m) and *A. indica* (9.13m) were higher and differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) from the other host species.

The results in table 7 (site seven) had fewer host species that consisted of *B. aegyptiaca*, *A. nilotica* and *A. indica* with DBH of 0.22m, 0.12m and 0.11m respectively which were significantly different ($P < 0.05$) from each other. The plant height of *B. aegyptiaca* (13.03m) and *A. indica* (13.63m) were not significantly different ($P < 0.05$), but differed significantly ($P > 0.05$) from *A. nilotica* (10.14m). The canopy spread of *A. nilotica* (7.88m) and *A. indica* (7.39m) were not significantly different ($P > 0.05$) but the two differed significantly ($P < 0.05$) from that of *B. aegyptiaca* (6.67m)

Azadirachta indica showed highest population distribution in most sites. This might be due to its invasive and weed status. *A. indica* is noted for its drought resistance. Normally it thrives in areas with sub-arid to sub-humid conditions, with an annual rainfall of 400–1,200 mm. It can grow in regions with an annual rainfall below 400 mm, but in such cases it depends largely on ground water levels. *Azadirachta indica* can grow in many different types of soil, but it thrives best on well drained deep and sandy soils (PIER, 2011). It is a tropical to subtropical tree with high tolerance to very high temperatures and exists at annual mean temperatures of 21–32 °C (70–90 °F) (Barstow and Deepu, 2018). *Azadirachta indica* had competitive and regenerative abilities than other plants and deprive them of water, lights and nutrients (Compact Oxford English Dictionary, 2013).

This research revealed that the species *Tapinanthus globiferus* was present in Wamakko, Sudan Savanna Ecological Zone. This was similar to Didier *et al.* (2009) who observed that in Samaru Zaria, Nigeria the infestation of trees by mistletoe was very high and generated great concern by the local people as the presence of mistletoe resulted in the reduction of vegetation and fruit production of trees in the region. Boussium *et al.* (2004) stated that abundance of this parasitic plant (mistletoe) can simultaneously parasitize many host species, since different host species may supply a parasite with different resources, a mixture of host tree species may be superior to a single host alone. The investigation of the level of occurrence of *Tapinanthus globiferus* on host Trees species in this research revealed that *Tapinanthus globiferus* was present in the study area with varying degree of infestation. This was in line with Kelly *et al.* (2000) and Bach *et al.* (2000) who noted that marginal and fragmented forests not only provide better habitats for mistletoes but also promote invasion of such habitats by mistletoes. The occurrence of some mistletoe at higher elevation is limited by environmental factors and is not related to host preference (Devkota *et al.*, 2015).

Azadirachta indica had the highest distribution across the sites but showed no infestation at UDUS and this could be due to the fact that *A. indica* at that site were younger individuals compared to other species. This result agreed with the findings of Rahmad *et al.* (2014), that larger trees received more mistletoe seeds as they served as better nesting place for birds. *Tapinanthus globiferus* infestation affected the growth parameters of host tree species in the study area. This was similar to the findings Press and Phoenix, (2005), who observed that concentrated host–parasite interactions, quantifying the effects of mistletoes was evaluated in the study locations that were investigated and found that *Tapinanthus* on host growth, and describing the processes of mistletoe dispersal and establishment. Subsequent research focused on several components of mistletoe–host interactions (Shaw *et al.*, 2005). *A. indica* had better growth characteristics than other species in terms of relative height, DBH, and canopy spread. This agreed with the findings of Rahmad *et al.* (2014) that trees with conical crown, had more mistletoes because they allow greater sunlight penetration due to larger gap they create at the top. It also agreed with the findings of Buen *et al.* (2002) that tall trees tend to attract more dispersers of mistletoes compared to shorter trees.

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